

**ASSESSMENT OF HEAVY METAL STATUS AROUND MAJOR INDUSTRIAL SITES IN
SOUTHERN CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA USING ATOMIC ABSORPTION
SPECTROPHOTOMETER (AAS) METHOD**

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ABSTRACT

This research focuses on assessment of heavy metal concentration in the soils of industrial areas in Southern Cross River State. Soil samples in the immediate vicinity of some selected industrial sites at 15cm deep were collected in five sample locations of Southern Cross River state which include, Gitto Company, Zenith construction Ltd. Faith Plant, and UNICEM. This was done to evaluate the status of heavy metals (Fe, Cd, Co, Cu, Pd, Cr, Zn, Ni & Mn) present. The soil samples were subjected to a total digestion technique using HNO₃ and HClO₄ acids and analyzed using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer for the metals stated above. The metal concentration in ppm in all the site ranges from 163.35ppm – 2262ppm for Fe, 18.80ppm – 33.25ppm for Cd, 3.53ppm – 4.48ppm for Co, 21.40ppm – 38.10ppm for Cu, 22.55ppm for Pb, 6.10ppm – 15.12 ppm for Cr, 9.50ppm – 44.35ppm for Zn, 5.40ppm – 46.30ppm for Ni and 10.43ppm – 64.20ppm for Mn. The concentration of the various heavy metals showed a wide range of variation with variable pattern in the order Fe>>Mn>Ni>Zn>Cu>Cd>Pd>Cr>Co in the entire sample area. Significant enrichments were obtained for Cd, Cu, and Zn respectively at Unicem, but Pb was not significantly enriched in any sample location. The contamination index in this study ranged from uncontaminated (0) to moderately contaminated (1-2). The concentration of heavy metals in this study falls below the regulatory standard of other countries apart from Cd, an element associated with quarry and mining activities, waste batteries, and metal finishing industrial waste having concentration above the regulatory level of other countries.

Keywords: Heavy metals, soil, quarry activities, industries, contamination.

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INTRODUCTION

Nigeria, being a developing country in the world today, is also a part of the industrialization process (Njoku *et al.*, 2013) and economic development. Industrial pollution is one of the causes of environmental hazards and will continue to be a vital cause of natural pollution. Rapid urbanization and industrialization releases enormous volume of heavy metals into our environment. Soils is recognized as a major sink (Adriana, 2003) for anthropogenic heavy metals deposition through various pathway.

Heavy metals are defined as metallic element that have a high relative density compared to water (Tchounnou *et al.*, 2012). Heavy metals is among one of the pollution which causes several threats to human and the environment (Cheng, 2003). And it is becoming more serious with urbanization, industrialization and modern agricultural activities. Heavy metals does not easily degrade or volatilized owing to their stable physical and chemical properties (Singh *et al.*, 2010, Adel *et al.*, 2012) therefore it has led to more serious and possibly irreversible pollution resulting from increasing heavy metal accumulation in soil every year (Zhang *et al.*, 2012). Due to this hazard posed by heavy metal in the soil determination is necessary as an indicator showing anthropogenic input in the environment.

A quarry is an open pit mine from which rocks or rock minerals are excavated through various process that may comprise removal of the topsoil, drilling, blasting with explosive and use of machinery to crush and grade rock materials and for transportation. Quarry as every mining operation is a destructive activity whose sociology economic benefits may be unable to compensate for the soil overall detrimental effects on natural ecosystem (Ayodele, *et al.*, 2014).

This study is aimed at determining the heavy metal content in soils of in the major industrial sites in Southern Cross River State which includes quarries and stone crushing facility.

MATERIALS AND METHOD.

Surface soils of 15cm deep were collected using soil auger from each of the sampling site. The exact location for all sample sites was determined using global positioning system and entered into a geographical information system for data processing. Fig 1 shows the sample sites. The collected soil samples were air dried under laboratory condition for three days and drives through a 2.00mm mesh wire (Ismail, 1993). Samples of 1g was weighed and digested with HNO₃ and HCLO₄ in the ratio 3:1 heated in a fume cupboard. The digested sample was filtered using No 1 Whatman filter and the filtrate was made up to 50ml with distilled water. Then taken for heavy metal analysis by AAS (Isang *et al.*, 2023). The concentration of Fe, Cd, Co, Cu, Pb, Cr, Zn, Ni, and Mn in the filtrate were determined using a flame atomic spectrophotometer using air acetylene flame with deuterium background correction. The light source, hallow cathode lamps were operated at the following analytical lines for each element: 252.3nm for Fe. 228.8nm for Cd, 327.4nm for Cu, 241.2nm for Co, 283.3nm for Pb, 359.4nm for Cr, 307.6nm for Zn, 231.1nm for Ni, and 280.1nm for Mn. After every determination, blanks and certified reference materials were also run to determine the precision and instrumental uncertainty.

DATA ANALYSIS

The environmental impact of metals and the pollution level in the end samples can be determined with the help of two parameters: (1) The enrichment factor (EF) and (2) geoaccumulation index (I_{geo}).

The enrichment factor (EF) due to its universal formula is a relatively simple and easy tool for

assessing the enrichment degree and comparing the contamination of different environmental media (Benhaddya and Hadjel, 2013) EF is used to determine the enrichment degree and comparing the contamination of different environmental media (Nowrouzi and Pourkhabbaz, 2014). Among the elements used to normalised the metal constituent for normalization have been Al, Fe and Sc.

Fig 1 Map of Southern senatorial district of Cross River State showing sampling sites.

The constituents chosen for this purpose should according to Nworouzi (2014) should not be altered. Therefore, for the purpose of this study, Fe was the metal used for normalisation because

its anthropogenic source is small compare to natural source. The formula for EF is expressed in equation 1 below.

$$EF(X) = \frac{\left(\frac{X}{Fe}\right)_{SAMPLE}}{\left(\frac{X}{Fe}\right)_{CONTROL}} \quad 1$$

Where EF (X) = enrichment factor for metal X,

(X/Fe) SAMPLE = ratio of concentration of metal X to normalised elements (Fe) in the sample.

(X/Fe) CONTROL = ratio of concentration of metal X to normalised elements (Fe) in a reference material such as the control sample Sutherland (2000)

Contamination categories recognized on the basis of the enrichment factors are:

EF < 1 No enrichment

EF < 2 depletion to minimal enrichment,

EF = 2-5 moderate enrichment,

EF = 5-20 significant enrichment,

EF = 20-40 very high enrichment,

EF >40 extremely high enrichment

Enrichment factor can be used to differentiate the metal originality from anthropogenic activities and those from natural procedures and to assess the degree of anthropogenic influence. When EF=1, then the elements are mainly derived from the crust or soul. When a certain element of EF was significantly greater than 1 and the average crustal components can show the contrast, the elements have been enriched.

Geo-accumulation index (Igeo) was to assess the extent of Pb, Cd, Cr, Cu, Co, Mn, Ni, Zn, and Fe pollution of the soil samples in the study area. Geo-accumulation index (Igeo) was first used by

Muller in 1969 as a tool that provides the extent of pollution of soil with regards to the background concentration of the polluted metal. Igeo formula is expressed in equation 2 below.

$$I_{geo} = \log_2 \frac{C_m \text{ SAMPLE}}{(1.5 * C_m \text{ BACKGROUND})^3} \quad 2$$

The factor 1.5 is introduced to minimize the effect of possible variations in the background values, C_m background which may be attributed to lithogenic variations in soils. The background values here is the control.

RESULTS

The results of the topsoil samples within the sampling area of the major industries in Southern Cross River as presented in table 1 while the concentration of element in the control experiment is presented in table 2.

TABLE 1: Concentration of elements (ppm) in different sample locations

Location	Fe	Cd	Co	Cu	Pb	Cr	Zn	Ni	Mn
Gitto	1800.01	31.60	N.D	21.40	N.D	11.53	23.90	46.30	39.80
Zenith	1672.50	33.25	3.53	28.20	N.D	15.12	28.10	23.35	64.20
Faith plant	2262.00	19.80	4.48	38.10	22.55	13.31	44.35	22.10	56.20
Unicem	163.35	18.80	4.31	35.75	N.D	6.10	9.50	5.40	10.43

N.D. stands for not detected.

Table 2: Concentration of elements in the control experiment

Element	Fe	Cd	Co	Mo	Cu	Pb	Cr	Zn	Mn	Ni
Concentration(ppm)	870.50	9.25	5.30	ND	11.05	4.20	7.24	18.32	14.01	7.72

Table 3: Enrichment factor.

LOCATIONS	Cd	Co	Cu	Pb	Cr	Zn	Ni	Mn
GITO	1.635	ND	1.505	ND	1.098	1.358	2.853	1.373
ZENITH	1.876	0.346	1.329	ND	1.019	1.729	1.570	2.384
FAITH PLANT	0.825	0.326	1.327	2.068	0.663	2.017	1.101	1.543
UNICEM	10.814	4.336	17.241	ND	4.480	5.942	3.727	3.967

Table 4: Geoaccumulation index

LOCATIONS	ELEMENTS								
	Fe	Cd	Co	Cu	Pb	Cr	Zn	Ni	Mn
Gitto	0.46	1.19	ND	0.37	ND	0.09	0.90	2.00	0.92
Zenith	0.36	1.26	-1.17	0.77	ND	0.48	1.14	1.01	1.16
Faith Plant	0.79	0.51	-0.83	1.20	1.83	0.29	1.79	0.93	1.42
UNICEM	-3.00	-0.66	-0.88	-0.83	ND	-0.83	-0.43	-1.10	-1.01

Fig 2: cluster bar of geoaccumulation index.

Fig 3: 3.D surface presentation of geoaccumulation index

DISCUSSION

Level of Heavy Metal in Top Soil

The concentration of Fe, Cd, Co, Cu, Pb, Cr, Zn, Ni and Mn in the topsoil sample within the 15cm depth from the study area were presented in table 1. the concentration of the various metals showed a wide range of variation with variable patterns in the order: Fe>Mn>Zn>Cu>Cd>Pb>Cr>Co. this pattern of heavy metal distribution is similar to the reports of Sultana *et al.*, (2012), and Zahir *et al.*, (2016), the concentration (ppm) of heavy metals in the soils samples ranges between 163.35ppm -2262.00ppm for Fe, 18.80ppm – 33.25ppm for Cd, 3.53ppm – 4.48ppm for Co, 9.30ppm – 38.10ppm for Cu, ND- 22.55ppm for Pb, 6.10ppm – 15.12ppm for Cr. 9.50ppm – 44.35ppm for Zn, 5.40ppm – 46.30ppm for Ni and 10.43ppm – 64.20ppm for Mn. According to Nirmal *et al.*, (2007) and Kabir *et al.*,(2012), the concentration of zinc in this study is below safe limit. As compared to the regulatory levels for soil concentration established between different countries as reported by Kabir *et al.*, (2012). Only cadmium is above safe limit. It is also found that heavy metals detected in this study is less than detected in a research carried out by Kodom *et al.*, (2012) in soil heavy metal pollution in an industrial zone of Kumasi Ghana using XFR. The highest concentration of heavy metal in this study is Fe and cobalt is the least.

Enrichment Factor.

Table 3 above shows the enrichment factor of the analysed elements in all the sample locations, cadmium with 1.652 and 1.870 respectively at Gitto and Zenith had depletion to minimal enrichment implying that the elements are mainly derived from crust or soil while Unicem with EF of 10.81 showed significant enrichment.

Cobalt with EF of 0.346 and 0.325 at Zenith and Faith Plant respectively had no enrichment while Unicem has moderate enrichment of 4.337.

Copper with EF values of 1.328 and 1.327 in Zenith and Faith plant respectively had minimal enrichment while Unicem had significant enrichment with EF value of 17.241. Lead had an EF value of 2.066 in Faith Plant which showed moderate enrichment.

Chromium with EF value of 0.707 at Faith Plant and 0.770 at Gitto had no enrichment. Depletion to minimal at Zenith with 1.086 while Unicem had moderate enrichment of 4.490.

Nickel with EF of 1.574 and 1.101 in Zenith and Faith Plant had depletion to minimal enrichment. Gitto with EF of 2.900 and Unicem with EF of 3.727 showed moderate enrichment.

Zinc at Gitto and Zenith quarry with EF of 1.356 and 1.716 had depletion to minimal enrichment while Faith Plant showed moderate enrichment of Zn with EF of 2.013. Unicem had significant enrichment of 5.942.

Manganese had EF of 1.373 and 1.543 at Gitto and Faith plant which showed depletion to minimal enrichment while Zenith and Unicem showed moderate enrichment of 2.384 and 3.967.

According to Barbieri (2016) the most appropriate and relevant procedure to calculate enrichment factor was to use reference material to determine from uncontaminated background obtained from soils from the area of interest. But in this study the control site was used which was further away from the sample sites. It is evident from the result that only Pb, Zn, Ni and Mn exhibit depletion to minimal enrichment. However on the basis of location only Unicem exhibit moderate to significant enrichment of Cd, Co, Cu, Cr, Zn, Ni, and Mn except Pb which was not detected.

GEOACCUMULATION INDEX

The Igeo was based on the description classes for increasing Igeo values proposed by Muller. There are as follows $I_{geo} = 0$ uncontaminated, $0 < I_{geo} \leq 1$ = uncontaminated to moderately contaminated, $1 < I_{geo} \leq 2$ = moderately contaminated, $2 < I_{geo} \leq 3$ = moderately to strongly contaminated, $3 < I_{geo} \leq 4$ = strongly contaminated, $4 < I_{geo} \leq 5$ = strongly to extremely contaminated, $I_{geo} > 5$ = extremely contaminated. This discussion is based on sample locations as shown in fig 2 and fig 3 above. Data in the table 4 above reveals that Unicem is contaminated. This may be due to the fact that the samples were not collected directly in the quarry site but within the vicinity. The negative value showed the lithogenic contamination as described by Sundrajan and Velmurugan (2016).

Gitto showed moderate contamination of soil by Cd and Ni which are as a result of anthropogenic sources. Cd and Ni mainly from mining and smelting of nonferrous metal (Gain *et al.*, 2014) hence the contamination as experienced in the sample area.

In Zenith location Cd, Zn, Ni and Mn showed moderate contamination. According to Nirmal *et al.*, (2007) and Kabir *et al.*, (2012) the concentration of zinc in this study is below safe limit. The contamination of this sampling sites with Cd and Zn is attributed to anthropogenic source other human activities.

Faith plant, this company specialises on supplies of quarry materials such as granite, dust, hard core stone base, asphalt, haulage and also specializes in tyre buffer services and road construction services. It is moderately contaminated with Mn, Zn, Pb, and Cu. The Pb and Zn here may be as a result of automobile combustion. Mn like other lithogenic element is relatively abundant in nature. The moderate contamination of Mn, Zn, Pb and Cu is due to anthropogenic source.

The contamination index in this study range from uncontaminated (<0) to moderately contaminated (1-2) as reported in Ashaka limestone quarry Unman *et al.*, (2016)

National geography news (2016) reported that aggregates and asphalt products of quarry when mixed together is used for road construction and rail track hence the location of Gitto, Faith Plant and Zenith company in these areas. The concentrations of heavy metals in this area falls within the maximum allowable limit as set by WHO as reported by Chiroma *et al.*, (2014) except for Cadmium which is above the maximum allowable limit in soil. On the average, Cu and Ni showed enriched concentration in this area similar to a report by Likuku *et al.*, (2013) in the superficial layer of soils windward the Selibi Phikwe copper nickel mine.

CONCLUSION

Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) was employed for the analysis of nine heavy metals such as Fe, Cd, Co, Cu, Pb, Cr, Zn, Ni, and Mn in the four industrial area of Southern Cross River State to ascertain if their concentration can pose problem to the environmental health. The results obtained undergo further treatment using enrichment factors, geoaccumulation, and bar charts. Significant enrichments were obtained for Cd, Cu and Zn respectively at Unicem but Co, Cr, Ni, Mn and Pb was not significantly enriched in any sample location.

The contamination index in this study range from uncontaminated to moderately contaminated as reported in Ashaka limestone quarry by Usman *et al.*, (2016). Gitto, Zenith and Faith Plant showed moderate contamination for Cd, Cu, Pb, Zn, Ni and Mn. The study area was uncontaminated with Fe, Co and Cr in all the sampling areas.

The anthropogenic activities in these areas gave rise to the heavy metal pollution. Although a lot

of agricultural activities goes on in this area alongside mining, care must be taken to ensure adequate control measure to release of these heavy metals to avoid absorption by plants and ingestion by humans and aquatic lives.

Though the concentrations of the various heavy metals in this study showed a wide range of variation with variable pattern in the order: Fe>>>Mn>Ni >Zn >Cu>Cd>Pb>Cr>Co when compared with the regulatory levels for soil metal concentration established between different countries, the concentration falls below the regulatory standard of other countries apart from Cd, an element associated with quarry and mining activities having concentration above the regulatory level of other countries.

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